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RELATIONS BETWEEN PHILIP V OF MACEDON AND THE THRACIANS IN THE COURSE OF THE SOCIAL WAR (220 – 217 B.C.)

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Abstract: *This article presents an attempt for identifying the relations between Philip V of Macedon (221 – 179 B.C.) and the Thracians in the course of the Social war (220 – 217 B.C.). The limited ancient sources – in the form of several short sentences in the works of Polybius, Pompeius Trogus/Justin and Titus Livy – are analyzed. Arguments in suggestion of military actions of the Macedonian king against the Thracians in 220 B.C. are proposed; it is specified that they probably were military clashes along the borders. The available sources about Thracians in the Macedonian army during the war in question are also considered; they formed a contingent different from those of the mercenaries. All the evidence presented are interpreted as reflections of the significance of Thrace and the Thracians in the politics of Philip V from the very beginning of his reign.*

Key words: *Ancient Balkans, Thracians, Macedonia, History, Hellenistic Age.*

Introduction

There is no comprehensive research on the Thracian-Macedonian relationships in the time of Philip V of Macedon (221 – 179 B.C.). Available are a few historical overviews on the political development of Ancient Thrace through the Hellenistic age¹, but in them is not paid sufficient attention to the king's early fights to this land and peoples², although it can be pretended that

¹ Most of these overviews only focus on the most important events, for which direct information is available, see: Danov, Christo M. *Die Thraker auf dem Ostbalkan von der hellenistischen Zeit bis zur Gründung Konstantinopels. Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt, Geschichte und Kultur Roms in Spiegel der neueren Forschung, II.* Berlin & New York: Walter De Gruyter, 1979, 72 sq.; Tacheva, Margarita. *Ancient History of the Bulgarian Lands through the Hellenistic and Roman Age.* Sofia: “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Press, 1997, 51 sq.; Petkov, Plamen. *Military-Political Relations of Thracian Rulers in the European Southeast between 230/229 B.C. – 45/46 A.D.* Veliko Tarnovo: Faber, 2011, 20-23; Delev, Peter. *From Koroupedion to the Beginning of the Third Mithridatic War (281 – 73 B.C.E.). A Companion to Ancient Thrace.* John Wiley & Sons, 2015, 63 sq.; Delev, Peter. *Ancient Thrace in the End of the 3rd and in the First Half of the 2nd Century B.C. Collection in Honor of XX Years Programs in Egyptology in the New Bulgarian University.* Sofia: Iztok-Zapad, 2017, 36 sq.

² Operations of Philip V near the frontiers of Macedonia through the first year of his reign are indicated (without any further details) by Danov, Op. cit., 72-73; Zhekov, Zhivko. *The Macedonians, Philip V and the Romans.* P. St. Petkov (ed.). *Through the Past to the Future –*

the importance of his Thracian policy has been noticed even by the ancient Romans³ and is clearly seen in all the works, dedicated to the study of his life and deeds.⁴ However, general observations and conclusions are not drawn by the modern scholars. The following lines are an attempt for contribution to this problematic through clarification of the earliest relations between Philip V and the Thracians, i.e., from the beginning of his reign to the end of the Social war (220 – 217 B.C.).⁵ That event is considered the first in which he – though quite young – demonstrated abilities and gained enormous prestige among his contemporaries⁶.

A Thracian Campaign in 220 B.C.

Just before the Battle of Thermopylae in 191 B.C. the Roman consul Manius Acilius Glabrio had delivered a speech, as Livy informs⁷, which aimed

In Honorem Margaritae Karamihova. Sofia: Prosveta, 2018, 118. The clashes with the Dardanians of the same time have been more carefully studied, see Papazoglu, Fanula. *The Central Balkan tribes in Pre-Roman times*. Amsterdam: Adolf M. Hakkert, 1978, 149-151.

³ Both Polybius and Livy convey words of T. Quinctius Flamininus about the significance of Macedonia as a kind of barrier against invasions of Thracians and other tribes against Greece, see Iliev, Jordan. Thracians in the Second Macedonian War (200 – 197 B.C.). *Hiperboreea*, 7(2), 118.

⁴ Thrace and the Thracians are mentioned in various contexts in all of them. In addition to the fundamental monograph of Walbank, Frank William. *Philip V of Macedon*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014, see also the recently published works of Nicholson, Emma Louise. *A Reassessment of Philip V. of Macedon in Polybios' Histories*. PhD Thesis. Newcastle University: School of History, Classics and Archaeology, 2015; Kleu, Michael. *Die Seepolitik Philipps V. von Makedonien*. Kleine Schriftenreihe zur Militär- und Marinegeschichte, Band 24. Bochum: Winkler, 2015; D'Agostini, Monica. *The Rise of Philip V. Kingship and Rule in the Hellenistic World*. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso, 2019.

⁵ Detailed accounts of this war are presented by Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 24-67; Kralli, Ioanna. *The Hellenistic Peloponnese: Interstate Relations*. A Narrative and Analytic History, from the Fourth Century to 146 B.C. Swansea: The Classical Press of Wales, 2017, 267-310. See also Meadows, Andrew. Polybius, Aratus, and the History of the 140th Olympiad. *Polybius and his World: Essays in Memory of F. W. Walbank*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013, 91-116.

⁶ Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 67 – “Indeed, perhaps the most striking feature of the war was the rapid increase in Philip's stature [...] In Greece his prestige was enormous...”; Čašule, Nikola. Philip V of Macedon. R. S. Bagnall, K. Brodersen, C. B. Champion, A. Erskine, S. R. Heubner (eds.). *The Encyclopedia of Ancient History*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd., 2013, 1 – “The Social War was an important success for Philip: it showed him to be in control of his court and army and greatly increased his prestige”; Nicholson, A Reassessment of Philip V, 19 – “By 217 B.C., four years after his succession, Philip has demolished the misconception that he was an ineffective youth and emerges as a politically and militarily capable king”.

⁷ The speeches in Livy were composed by him, as proves their lexical analysis, but there is no reason to doubt the veracity of the facts reported in them. See for instance Gruen, Erich S.

to motivate the legions he led against the armies of Antiochus III the Great and his Hellenic allies. In the speech itself, to highlight the military glory of the Romans and their previous successes in the Balkans (i.e., in the Second Macedonian war, 200 – 197 B.C.), the consul expressed a brief but remarkably interesting characteristic of Philip V of Macedon:

“Rex ille bellicosissimus et exercitatus iam inde ab iuuenta finitimis Thracum atque Illyriorum et circa omnium accolarum bellis ... / that king was most devoted to war and trained from youth up in wars with the neighboring Thracians and Illyrians and all the inhabitants round about ...” (Liv. 36.17.6)⁸.

From this sentence it becomes clear that at an early age Philip V fought against the Thracians. There are no other details about the wars mentioned, such as their duration, end results and any more specific location in time and space. In the available scientific literature on the political history of Ancient Thrace the information quoted is not commented. Presented in this context that evidence – although it is quite vague – deserves more considered attention, not just because the Thracians are listed first, but also in view of the possibility for interpretation in context of other incomplete sources on early interactions of the Macedonian king with his neighbors.

The information itself is dated very generally. The only clarification available – the Latin word *iuuenta* (period of youth)⁹ – indicates that the wars in question should be sought towards the very beginning of the long reign of Philip V.

In fact, his participation in hostilities is possible only after 224 B.C., when he “*entered the School of Royal Pages to be educated at court, to hunt with the king and to fight alongside him in war*”.¹⁰ There is no information about clashes between Macedonians and Thracians with participation of Philip V from the specified year to the summer of 221 B.C., when he took the Macedonian throne at only 17 years old.¹¹ From the same time there are no other biographical details regarding Philip V, which does not exclude explanations as losing the entire

The Hellenistic World and the Coming of Rome. Berkley, Los Angeles, London: University of California Press, 1986, 275; Briscoe, John. *A Commentary on Livy, Books 41-45*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012, 339-340.

⁸ English translation after Livy, Titus. *History of Rome, Book 36* (Edited and translated by J. C. Yardley). Harvard University Press, 2018, 152-153.

⁹ For the translation of *iuuenta* and *iuventus* see Glare, P. G. W. et al. *Oxford Latin Dictionary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996, 988.

¹⁰ Cited after Hammond, N. G. L., F. W. Walbank. *A History of Macedonia, volume III: 336 – 167 B.C.* Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001, 368.

¹¹ The available data about the early biography of Philip V are discussed in Hammond & Walbank, *Op. cit.*, 369 sq.; Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 18 sq.; Nicholson, A Reassessment of Philip V, 3, 133 sq.; D’Agostini, *Op. cit.*, 39 sq.

ancient tradition or just because these events left out of view of any ancient writers.¹² However, in the current state of research, it seems more likely his first military operations against the Thracians to be sought immediately before and at the very beginning of the Social war (220 – 217 B.C.), because from the same time there are some other – also very general in nature – evidences of operations, led by Philip V along the Macedonian frontiers, which seem to correlate with the information, presented by Livy through Glabrio’s speech.

Earliest in chronological terms is a statement of Polybius. He tells about dispositions of the Macedonian king for securing his possessions in the beginning of the war:

“Φίλιππος δὲ παραχειμάζων ἐν Μακεδονίᾳ κατέγραφε τὰς δυνάμεις πρὸς τὴν μέλλουσαν χρεῖαν ἐπιμελῶς, ἅμα δὲ τούτοις ἠσφαλίζετο τὰ πρὸς τοὺς ὑπερκειμένους τῆς Μακεδονίας βαρβάρους / While wintering in Macedonia Philip spent his time in diligently levying troops for the coming campaign, and in securing his frontiers from attack by the barbarians of the interior” (Polyb. 4.29.1)¹³.

Unfortunately, here is not specified in more detail what exactly mean these frontier security measures. It seems that they were relatively effective, at least for a while, in neutralizing the permanent danger from neighboring tribes, as far as in characteristic of the Macedonian king the same author noted elsewhere in his work that although Philip V was frequently called away from his lands owing to the Social war:

“Βαρβάρων οὐδεὶς ἄψασθαι τῆς Μακεδονίας / none of the barbarous tribes on his frontier ventured to touch Macedonia” (Polyb. 7.11.4)¹⁴.

Although very general in nature, this statement does not exclude the Thracians, who were among the neighboring tribes. In any case, these words are an indicator of high authority of the Macedonian king, undoubtedly won in the first years of his reign.

The next report is found in Marcus Junianus Justinus’ Epitome of the Philippic History of Pompeius Trogus:

“Philippum Dardani ceterique omnes finitimi populi, quibus uelut inmortale odium cum Macedonum regibus erat, contemptu aetatis adsidue lacessebant.

¹² Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 18-19 notes that there are no records for the youth of Philip V, but it can be assumed – according to later demonstrated by him skills – the receiving of excellent training in military strategy and tactics.

¹³ English translation after Polybius. *The Histories*, volume II: Books 3-4 (Translated by W. R. Paton, revised by F. W. Walbank and Christian Habicht). Loeb Classical Library 137. Harvard University Press, 2011, 406-407.

¹⁴ English translation after Polybius. *The Histories*, volume III: Books 5-8 (Translated by W. R. Paton, revised by F. W. Walbank and Christian Habicht). Loeb Classical Library 138. Harvard University Press, 2011, 470-471.

Contra ille submotis hostibus non contentus sua defendisse ultro etiam Aetolis bellum inferre gestiebat / As to Philip, the Dardanians, and all the neighboring people, who cherished, as it were, an immortal hatred to the kings of the Macedonians, were perpetually molesting him in contempt of his youth. He, on the other hand, after repulsing his enemies, was not content with having defended his own dominions, but manifested the greatest eagerness to make war upon the Aetolians” (Iust. 29.1.10-11 = Trog. Prol. 29)¹⁵.

Particularly important here is the provided information for molesting (laccesso) of the Macedonian lands from all neighboring peoples; after Philip V managed to repulse them, he focused his attention to the Social war against the Aetolians. Summarized in this way, the information overlaps with that of Polybius, already presented above. Chronological landmarks are the mention of king’s youth and the military actions against the Aetolians.

Indeed, all the quoted passages are characterized by their very general nature. Despite the insufficient details, a combination of all of them allows the generation of new knowledge about the earliest contacts of Philip V with the Thracians.

The messages of Polybius and of Pompeius Trogus/Justin were referred by themselves to the Social war (220 – 217 B.C.), while that of Livy was not related to the same war. The only one reference point for its dating is the noted “youthful age” of Philip V, which corresponds to Pompeius Trogus/Justin’s emphasis on the youth of the Macedonian king as a reason for activation of the Macedonian neighbors.¹⁶ Therefore, it can be suggested that the three authors narrate about one and the same military actions. Although with justification *ex silentio*, the evidence of Livy should refer to 220 B.C. and thus can supplement the information given by Polybius and Pompeius Trogus/Justin.

The general course of the Social war also points to that year. Namely through attacks of Macedonian neighbors, neglected by Polybius in his exposition, Nicholas Hammond explains the absence of Macedonian military actions in Greece until the end of 220 B.C.¹⁷ Pompeius Trogus/Justin does not name the Thracians directly, but it is very probable that exactly these actions were envisaged by Glabrio in his words, transmitted by Livy. So, it can be assumed that the three authors are an independent of each other source for one

¹⁵ English translation after *Justin, Cornelius Nepos, and Eutropius* (Literary translated by John Selby Watson). London: Henry J. Bohn, 1853, 214.

¹⁶ According to Polybius (4.3.2; 4.5.3) the Aetolians also decided to fight because of the youth of the Macedonian king. See McGing, Brian. *Youthfulness in Polybius: The Case of Philip V of Macedon. Polybius and his World: Essays in Memory of F. W. Walbank*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013, 181-200.

¹⁷ Hammond & Walbank, *Op. cit.*, 369 – “Although overlooked by Polybius, these attacks help to explain the failure of the Macedonian army to act in southern Greece until late 220”.

and the same events with Thracian participation near the frontiers of the Macedonian kingdom.

Among the three authors, only Livy names directly the Thracians as opponents of the Macedonian king, while the other two undoubtedly incorporate them among the Macedonian neighbors: Polybius refers to “the barbarians of the interior” and Pompeius Trogus/Justin to “all the neighboring people”.

The combination of all the presented testimonies enables recognition in the measures, mentioned by Polybius, of military operations against the immediate neighbors of Macedonia. Such are attested in later time and represent an integral part of Philip's Thracian policy. A good parallel is the story of Livy about preventive military actions against the Maedi through the First Macedonian war (215 – 205 B.C.).¹⁸ An argument in support of such a decision is also the consistency of Polybius' message: first is the careful recruitment of troops for the forthcoming military campaign in Greece and only then was the security of the frontiers.

Thracians on Macedonian service

Another thematic circle in relation with the Thracian policy of Philip V is formed by the attested Thracians in the Macedonian army. They are known by two testimonies of Polybius, who writes that in 219 B.C. the Dardanians went to the possessions of the Macedonian king, but:

“ἀκούσαντες οἱ Δαρδάνιοι παρὰ Θρακῶν τινῶν αὐτομόλων τὴν παρουσίαν τοῦ Φιλίππου, καταπλαγέντες παραχρῆμα διέλυσαν τὴν στρατείαν, καίπερ ἤδη σύνεγγυς ὄντες τῆς Μακεδονίας / the Dardanians, hearing of his arrival from some Thracian deserters, took fright and at once dismissed their army, although they were now close to Macedonia” (Polyb. 4.66.6-7)¹⁹.

No more details are given about the Thracians in question. They are defined as “probably mercenaries” by some scholars, while others do not commit to their determination²⁰. It seems rather that these Thracians were on service at Philip V, maybe by some obligation, because it is hard to believe that mercenaries would desert. It is unclear why they went to the lands of the Dardanians, instead to Thrace.

¹⁸ Liv. 26.25.1-2. This information is reviewed and commented by all authors in the field of Thracology, see: Danov, Op. cit., 73; Tacheva, Op. cit., 53; Petkov, Op. cit., 27-29; Delev, From Koroupedion, 64; Delev, Ancient Thrace, 38.

¹⁹ English translation after Polybius, vol. II, 500-501.

²⁰ Walbank, Frank William. A Historical Commentary on Polybius, volume I. Commentary on Books I – VI. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1957, 521. They “*were Thracian mercenaries in Macedonia, probably on garrison duty*”, according to Griffith, G. T. *The Mercenaries of the Hellenistic World*. Cambridge: The University Press, 2014, 70, but arguments are not provided.

In the following 218 B.C. some Thracians participated in the campaign of the Macedonian king in Aetolia.²¹ In the absence of other information, their position in the army is important:

“διὸ καὶ παντελῶς στενήν καὶ δυσδίωδον ἔχει τὴν πάροδον – μετὰ δὲ ταῦτα τοὺς μὲν μισθοφόρους προθέμενος πάσης τῆς πορείας, ἐπὶ δὲ τούτοις τοὺς Ἰλλυριοὺς, ἐξῆς δὲ τοὺς πελταστὰς καὶ φαλαγγίτας ἔχων προῆγε διὰ τῶν στενῶν, ἀπουραγούτων μὲν αὐτῶ τῶν Κρητῶν, δεξιῶν δὲ παρὰ πλάγια τῶν Θρακῶν καὶ ψιλῶν ἀντιπαραπορευομένων ταῖς χώραις / [Philip V] putting his mercenaries at the head of the column, the Illyrians behind them, and last of all the peltasts and heavy-armed soldiers, he advanced through the pass, with the Cretans guarding his rear and the Thracians and light-armed troops advancing parallel to him through the country on his right flank” (Polyb. 5.7.10-11)²².

So, it becomes clear that the Thracians formed a contingent, different from those of the mercenaries.²³ Unfortunately, essential characteristics of these Thracians are not specified, such as number and tribal affiliation. From the context it is clear, that they were light infantry. Nothing more was reported about their participation in the subsequent operations of the Macedonian king.²⁴

With the available information, it seems more likely that the Thracian contingent participated in the Macedonian army according to agreements, achieved by one of the predecessors of Philip V and continued by himself. An argument in support of such an assumption is a fragmentary statement, in which a Thracian named Bithys, commander of Demetrius II (239 – 229 B.C.) was mentioned. Maybe in 233/232 B.C. he entered in Peloponnese and defeated the Achaeans, led by Aratus, at Phylacia.²⁵ More information about him is not known. Some modern scholars recognized him in a decree granting Athenian

²¹ On this campaign see Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 54 sq.; Nicholson, A Reassessment of Philip V, 83-109; Nicholson, Emma Louise. Polybios, the Laws of War, and Philip V of Macedon. *Historia*, 67(4), 2018, 434-453; D’Agostini, Op. cit., 110 sq.

²² English translation after Polybius, vol. III, 22-23.

²³ Griffith, Op. cit., 70 writes that “... *Thracians are more likely to have been mercenaries than anything else*”. According to Walbank, A Historical Commentary, 545 “*Whether the Thracians were mercenaries ... is unclear*”.

²⁴ Later in his work Polybius talks about the plunder of the Thermae plain and the city of Thermos from the Macedonian king and his troops. It has been suggested that “*Thracian peltast, serving as mercenaries to the Antigonids, also take part in the plunder*” – cited after Petkov, Op. cit., 21. Such an assumption seems plausible from the logic of the text, but there is no direct message from Polybius about Thracian participation in these actions.

²⁵ Hammond & Walbank, Op. cit., 331-332; Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 13. The source is Plut., Arat., 34.1-2: “διὸ καὶ κρατηθέντος αὐτοῦ μάχη περὶ Φυλακίαν ὑπὸ Βίθυος τοῦ Δημητρίου στρατηγοῦ, καὶ λόγου γενομένου πολλοῦ μὲν, ὡς ἐάλωκε, πολλοῦ δὲ ὡς τέθνηκεν, ὁ μὲν τὸν Πειραιᾶ φρουρῶν Διογένης ἔπεμψεν ἐπιστολὴν εἰς Κόρινθον ἐξίστασθαι τῆς πόλεως κελεύων τοὺς Ἀχαιοὺς ...”.

citizenship, but this remains debatable, because according to other researchers the person in question is rather an associate of Lysimachus of the same name²⁶, and the paleographic features of the inscription indicate earlier dating.²⁷ Most important here is that this message demonstrate presence of Thracians with leading functions in the Macedonian army before the reign of Philip V.

It is interesting to note that at the same time Thracian contingents were documented also in the armies of the other two most important Hellenistic states, i.e., Egypt of the Ptolemies and Syria of the Seleucids.²⁸

Conclusions

The presented analysis of the available ancient information clearly shows that there are enough arguments to determine the first known military clash between Philip V and the Thracians in 220 B.C. It is worth noting that the proposed interpretation of the fragmentary and incomplete ancient sources will remain only a possible hypothesis until confirmation of new reliable evidence. The proposed campaign, however, seems highly likely, because, except that it fits well in the context of the available information about the Social war, also allows an explanation of Livy's information on wars of Philip V against the Thracians during his youth. A whole decade after that any contacts between the Macedonian king and the Thracians are not known²⁹; his military plans were focused on Greece and the Western Balkans.³⁰

In addition, the available ancient sources, presumably the above-cited message of Polybius (Polyb. 7.11.4), explicitly reports the high authority of Philip V among his neighbors – to which the Thracians also belong – in the first years after his accession to the Macedonian throne, but unfortunately without specifying how it was achieved. The proposed here operations against the Thracians in 220 B.C. provides opportunity for explanation of the authority gained. Moreover, these probably were a matter of actions on a large enough scale, after they managed to enter (albeit without much detail) in the works of ancient writers. So, through the Social war Philip V fought with success on

²⁶ Delev, Peter. *Lysimachus*. Sofia: “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Press, 2004, 330-331.

²⁷ Grabowski, Tomasz. The Ptolemies versus the Achaean and Aetolian Leagues in the 250s – 220s BC. *Electum: Studia z historii starożytnej*, XIX, 2012, 93 with literature.

²⁸ In the Battle of Raphia on 22 June 217 B.C., in which the outcome of the IV Syrian war (219 – 217 B.C.) was decided, Thracians even participated in support of the two warring states, see Polyb. 5.65.10-11; 5.79.6; 5.82.6. Numerical values and other characteristics of the Thracians are not specified in each case and that prevents attempts to comparisons and formulation of more definite observations.

²⁹ It is possible that some actions were not noted by the ancient writers. An instance is the Philip V's letter to the people of Larissa, dated to 215/214 B.C., in which an expedition (probably to the north) is mentioned. See a commentary in Papazoglu, Op. cit., 151.

³⁰ See in more detail Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 67 sq.

several fronts. His authority in Greece is traditionally explained with the successes in the Social war³¹, while that among the Macedonian neighbors, perceived through the short sentence of Polybius, should be explained with the operations, an echo of which are all the commented in this work ancient sources.

It is not possible to locate the actions of Philip V more precisely, due to limited information and incomplete knowledge of the political map of Ancient Thrace. Proposed are only assumptions for delineating the frontiers of the Macedonian state, without it being possible to fix a secure eastern border of Macedonian interests; during the time in question, it is hardly to believe that the latter crossed Mesta River.³²

Immediately after the ascent of Philip V some Thracians are attested in the Macedonian army. They were not mercenaries. Although incidental, these mentions testify for a traditional and permanent Thracian presence in the army of the Macedonian king – a circumstance well documented also in later events.³³

It seems that at the very beginning of his reign Philip V had allies in Thrace, although their names are unknown. The presence of a Thracian contingent in the Macedonian army, different from the mercenaries, raises this question, but not any guidelines for its answer.

References

1. Briscoe, John. *A Commentary on Livy, Books 41-45*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012.
2. Čašule, Nikola. Philip V of Macedon. R. S. Bagnall, K. Brodersen, C. B. Champion, A. Erskine, S. R. Heubner (eds.). *The Encyclopedia of Ancient History*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd., 2013, DOI: 10.1002/9781444338386.webeah09190.
3. D'Agostini, Monica. *The Rise of Philip V*. Kingship and Rule in the Hellenistic World. Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orsp, 2019.
4. Danov, Christo M. Die Thraker auf dem Ostbalkan von der hellenistischen Zeit bis zur Gründung Konstantinopels. *Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt, Geschichte und Kultur Roms in Spiegel der neueren Forschung, II*. Berlin & New York: Walter De Gruyter, 1979, 21-185.
5. Delev, Peter. *Lysimachus*. Sofia: “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Press, 2004 (published in Bulgarian).

³¹ See above, Not. 7.

³² On the Macedonian frontiers at the very beginning of Philip V's reign see Walbank, Philip V of Macedon, 11; Kleu, Op. cit., 247.

³³ For instance, see Iliev, Op. cit., 109-121, with analysis of the Thracian participation in the Second Macedonian war (200 – 197 B.C.).

6. Delev, Peter. From Koroupedion to the Beginning of the Third Mithridatic War (281 – 73 B.C.E.). *A Companion to Ancient Thrace*. John Wiley & Sons, 2015, 59-74.
7. Delev, Peter. Ancient Thrace in the End of the 3rd and in the First Half of the 2nd Century B.C. *Collection in Honor of XX Years Programs in Egyptology in the New Bulgarian University*. Sofia: Iztok-Zapad, 2017, 36-50 (published in Bulgarian).
8. Glare, P. G. W. et al. *Oxford Latin Dictionary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996.
9. Grabowski, Tomasz. The Ptolemies versus the Achaean and Aetolian Leagues in the 250s – 220s BC. *Electum: Studia z historii starożytnej*, XIX, 2012, 83-97.
10. Griffith, G. T. *The Mercenaries of the Hellenistic World*. Cambridge: The University Press, 2014 (first published 1935).
11. Gruen, Erich S. *The Hellenistic World and the Coming of Rome*. Berkley, Los Angeles, London: University of California Press, 1986.
12. Hammond, N. G. L., F. W. Walbank. *A History of Macedonia, volume III: 336 – 167 B.C.* Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001.
13. Iliev, Jordan. Thracians in the Second Macedonian War (200 – 197 B.C.). *Hiperboreea*, 7(2), 109-121, 2020, DOI: 10.5325/hiperboreea.7.2.0109.
14. *Justin, Cornelius Nepos, and Eutropius* (Literary translated by John Selby Watson). London: Henry J. Bohn, 1853.
15. Kleu, Michael. *Die Seepolitik Philipps V. von Makedonien*. Kleine Schriftenreihe zur Militär- und Marinegeschichte, Band 24. Bochum: Winkler, 2015.
16. Kralli, Ioanna. *The Hellenistic Peloponnese: Interstate Relations*. A Narrative and Analytic History, from the Fourth Century to 146 B.C. Swansea: The Classical Press of Wales, 2017.
17. Livy, Titus. *History of Rome, Book 36* (Edited and translated by J. C. Yardley). Harvard University Press, 2018, DOI: 10.4159/DLCL.livy-history_rome_36.2018.
18. McGing, Brian. Youthfulness in Polybius: The Case of Philip V of Macedon. *Polybius and his World: Essays in Memory of F. W. Walbank*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013, 181-200, DOI: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199608409.003.0009.
19. Meadows, Andrew. Polybius, Aratus, and the History of the 140th Olympiad. *Polybius and his World: Essays in Memory of F. W. Walbank*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013, 91-116, DOI: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199608409.003.0004.

20. Nicholson, Emma Louise. *A Reassessment of Philip V. of Macedon in Polybios' Histories*. PhD Thesis. Newcastle University: School of History, Classics and Archaeology, 2015.
21. Nicholson, Emma Louise. Polybios, the Laws of War, and Philip V of Macedon. *Historia*, 67(4), 2018, 434-453.
22. Papazoglu, Fanula. *The Central Balkan tribes in Pre-Roman times*. Amsterdam: Adolf M. Hakkert, 1978.
23. Petkov, Plamen. *Military-Political Relations of Thracian Rulers in the European Southeast between 230/229 B.C. – 45/46 A.D.* Veliko Tarnovo: Faber, 2011 (published in Bulgarian).
24. Polybius. *The Histories*, volume II: Books 3-4 (Translated by W. R. Paton, revised by F. W. Walbank and Christian Habicht). Loeb Classical Library 137. Harvard University Press, 2011, DOI: 10.4159/DLCL.polybius-histories.2010.
25. Polybius. *The Histories*, volume III: Books 5-8 (Translated by W. R. Paton, revised by F. W. Walbank and Christian Habicht). Loeb Classical Library 138. Harvard University Press, 2011, DOI: 10.4159/DLCL.polybius-histories.2010.
26. Tacheva, Margarita. *Ancient History of the Bulgarian Lands through the Hellenistic and Roman Age*. Sofia: “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Press, 1997 (published in Bulgarian).
27. Walbank, Frank William. *A Historical Commentary on Polybius*, volume I. Commentary on Books I – VI. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1957.
28. Walbank, Frank William. *Philip V of Macedon*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014 (first published 1940).
29. Zhekov, Zhivko. The Macedonians, Philip V and the Romans. P. St. Petkov (ed.). *Through the Past to the Future – In Honorem Margaritae Karamihova*. Sofia: Prosveta, 2018, 112-123 (published in Bulgarian).